

D5.4 Communication Toolkit

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, under Grant Agreement No 101101521

September 2023

D5.4 Communication Toolkit

Project Acronym	AMON
Project Title	Development of a next generation AMmONia FC system.
Type	HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
Project Coordinator	Matteo Testi (FBK)
Project Duration	January 1, 2023 – December 31, 2025 (36 Months)
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Contributing beneficiary(ies)	-
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Introduction

This deliverable describes the communication materials produced since the beginning of AMON project to support the dissemination and communication (D&C) activities, with the intention to customize the delivered messages depending on the specific targets.

But what is the main purpose of having a wide range of communication materials? The goal is to tailor communication to carry it out more effectively and maximise the impact of project results, providing tools and appropriate messages to reach and attract multiple stakeholders, who might demonstrate interest in exploiting the technology developed in AMON.

The materials are available in the folder shared with all the Partners, who are warmly invited to use these ready-made tools to provide accurate and distinguishable information.

This deliverable is based on D5.2 “Visual Identity” as the communication materials have common graphical elements. They are based on the visual identity that characterize AMON as a distinguishable brand. In the deliverable D5.2 the conceptualisation process and results of the logo, colour palette and payoff have been described. Some communication materials were also anticipated, and a description of the website was given. The toolkit will also be fundamental to support the strategy, that will be outlined in D5.3 “DEC Plan”, to engage with external stakeholders, communicating the state of art of activities and fostering the exploitation of the project results.

The communication materials have been created by Communication and Design (eDesign), an external contractor chosen to support the team of Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) in designing the visual identity of the project. It is important to underline that all Partners have been involved in the creation of the communication materials.

The document is structured in four main sections. The first chapter explains the importance of the communication toolkit and the need to have different materials, depending on the target the project is addressing to. Chapter 2 summarises the main elements of the visual identity, described in detail in D5.2, and focuses on the conceptualisation of the main image created which is then used in different forms on the various materials. The third and fourth sections concentrates on the tools: chapter 3 describes the communication materials already created, while chapter 4 outlines the plans for the next possible tools, which will be designed starting from the summer 2024 until the end of the project, when more information and concrete results will be available.

01. What is a Communication Toolkit?

Communication is fundamental in EU Projects for two main reasons: first, beneficiaries of EU funding receive public money, and communication shows how the public money is spent and the outcomes, thus increases the trust from society. Secondly, communication can attract the attention of policy makers and, consequently, additional funding to continue the research and development activities.¹

A communications toolkit is a collection of materials created to send a specific message to a targeted audience. It is helpful to amplify messages and create focused communications.

Communication activities support the dissemination and exploitation tasks of the AMON project as provides it with a distinguishable brand, thanks to the creation of a visual identity, and public visibility. These activities imply the passage of information through appropriate messages, channels and tools which address specific stakeholders.

The main target groups of AMON have been identified at proposal stage and are numerous and different from each other's, as they have been linked to the specific outcomes of the project and its impacts. However, the main target groups can be considered those related to

- Global scientific community: scientists, researchers, and academia
- Industrial community: investors, businesses, FC-industrial players, system integrators and end users in target sectors
- Decision and policy makers: national, European, and international institutions, regulators and standardisation bodies, NGOs
- General Public: citizens, students, and PhD

It is fundamental to have a regularly updated D&C Plan which will guide the Consortium in the promoting, informing, and raising awareness and interest on the importance of developing the next generation of renewable energy technology to build a decarbonized and sustainable economy and society in EU and worldwide.

Table 1 reports the main communication materials that will be used to reach stakeholders and outlines their specific purpose and possible use.

Table 1. AMON Main Communication Materials

Name of material	Stakeholder field	Goal	Events
Website and social media	General public	Communicate to the most possible number of people and stakeholders, informing and attracting, Establish a	-

¹ Information taken from https://eic.ec.europa.eu/communication-toolkit_en

		close relationship with targeted audience	
Templates: <i>Poster, PowerPoint, and Word</i>	All	Raise awareness and disseminate with the distinguishable brand of AMON, and the logo plus acknowledgement to the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.	Internal meeting, external events.
Branding Guidelines	Investors, industrial partners	Guides the partners and stakeholders in the use of the logo, acknowledgement, and materials.	-
Roll-up	All	Attract and inform	Events organised by the project, fairs, etc.
GIF / short videos	General Public	Animated image that represents complex concepts with clear and concise message	Online material
Flyer	All	Promote the main activity, partners, and objective of the project. Reach the audience with few and concise information, giving the contact details	Distribution via email or at events to multiple stakeholders
Video	All	Engage, arouse the viewer interest, and communicate concretely the results	Online, events
Factsheet	Industrial stakeholders, Investors, Policy makers	Provide information on a specific topic in an easy- and quick-to-read format, with images, graphs, and data. Engage for future exploitation	Online, targeted events and scientific conferences
Final Brochure	Industrial stakeholders, Investors, Policy makers	Describe in a detailed manner the results and installation in user cases to raise interest and create best practices. Engage for future exploitation	Final event, scientific conferences

02 The starting point

Communication materials are successful when there is a well-designed visual identity which reflects the mission and concept of the project.

2.1 AMON Visual Identity

As reported in the introduction, AMON visual identity is described in detail in deliverable D5.2. However, it is fundamental to underline that visual identity guarantees that the stakeholders and audience which relate to AMON project have clearly understood who their interlocutor is. Visual identity presents the project to internal and external stakeholders, it tells a story through the visual communications. It includes a logo, imagery, typography, colours, and creative design that characterize a project as a distinguishable brand.

The creation of the logo started with the identification of the basic, core concepts. The project AMON aims to develop a novel system for the utilization and conversion of ammonia into electric power at high efficiency using a solid oxide fuel cell system. Sustainability, green energy, and power are fundamental words. These concepts have then been transformed in colours and in the logo which is characterized by the NH_3 molecule that locates itself on the final part of the lettering. Another strong element is the symbol of the ignition "ON" which, as integral part of the name, payoff "from ammonia to power" emphasises the message that the project wishes to give.

Figure 1. AMON Logo

The visual identity also comprises the logo of the Clean Hydrogen Partnership alongside the EU flag and the acknowledgement, which cites *"The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, under Grant Agreement No 101101521"*.

Once established the visual identity, the attention was drawn on the main actor of the project which is the technology that will be developed in AMON.

2.2 The main actor

The Project Coordinator and the partners wished to have an image that clearly explained the preliminary structure of the technology, showing all components and flows.

Therefore, the first step has been that to define in detail the graph of the flows and processes:

Figure 2. AMON Flows

The second step was to transform this graph into 3D images, which should have to be realistic and thus supporting materials and reference images were requested to the Partners.

Figure 3. AMON Technology with all the different components

The third and final step has been that to recreate the possible environments and situations where the technology could be used and the team identified: the harbours and port industry (main focus in the AMON Project), and the stationary use in industries and in the telecommunication sector.

Figure 4. AMON Technology and its possible applications

It is worth noting that the involvement of all Partners has been fundamental to understand the correct flows of the technology, the identification of the components, and the determination of the most appropriate applications of AMON.

All Partners have been actively involved in the conceptualization of the visual identity and the design of the reference images that have been used to create the communication toolkit.

03 The available tools

This chapter introduces the tools available at this stage in the project. This first collection of materials will be then enriched by other instruments to present the developments of AMON results.

3.1 Template

The visual identity of AMON has been used to design the template for Power Point presentations (Figure 5), and for Word document (Figure 6). The templates are important elements of the visual identity since they help to characterize the project AMON as brand in presentations and other external D&C activities, as well as in public documents. Templates have been made available to project partners.

Figure 5. AMON Template for Power Point Presentation

FBK - Fondazione Bruno Kessler - Italy

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, under Grant Agreement No. 101012161

[\(Project View\)](#)

DXX TITLE

Project Acronym	AMON
Project Title	Development of a next generation Ammonia FC system
Type	HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
Project Coordinator	Matteo 2024 (FBK)
Project Duration	January 1, 2023 - December 31, 2025 (36 Months)
Deliverable No.	DX-X
Dissemination Level	PU/SEN
Work Package	WP-X - Title
Task	TX - Title
Lead beneficiary	T (FBK) / 2 (SEI) / 3 (VITI) / 4 (DTU) / 5 (KWA NL) / 6 (KWA IT) / 7 (ALSW) / 8 (ALDO) / 9 (ALIT) / 10 (SAPIO) / 11 (EPFL) / 12 (EPFC) / 13 (HSLU)
Contributing beneficiary(s)	T (FBK) / 2 (SEI) / 3 (VITI) / 4 (DTU) / 5 (KWA NL) / 6 (KWA IT) / 7 (ALSW) / 8 (ALDO) / 9 (ALIT) / 10 (SAPIO) / 11 (EPFL) / 12 (EPFC) / 13 (HSLU)
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1.0			
2.0			
3.0			
4.0			

01. Introduction

The kick-off meeting of the project AMON "Development of a next generation Ammonia FC system" was held on 29 January 2023 in Trento, hosted by Fondazione Bruno Kessler, and followed by a visit to the manufacturing site of Solid Oxide Technology by Sulystria in Pergine. All Partners were present to launch the activities of this Horizon Europe project, which will last for 3 years and is funded from the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.

The overarching objective of AMON project is to develop a novel system for the utilization and conversion of ammonia into electric power at high efficiency using a solid oxide fuel cell system. The project will deal with the design of the basic components of the system including the fuel cell, an ammonia burner, ammonia resistant heat exchangers, the engineering of the whole balance of plants, and validation of the compliance with ammonia use for all the specific parts and components. Customarily, depending on system needs, an ammonia cracker and waste gas recirculation will be developed. The outputs of the questionnaire analysis are:

- Point 01:** Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullam corporis suscipit laboriosam, nisi ut aliquid ex ea commodi consequatur. Duis aute laborum reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.
- Point 02:** Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullam corporis suscipit laboriosam, nisi ut aliquid ex ea commodi consequatur. Duis aute laborum reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.
- Point 03:** Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullam corporis suscipit laboriosam, nisi ut aliquid ex ea commodi consequatur. Duis aute laborum reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

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01. Introduction

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- Point 02:** Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullam corporis suscipit laboriosam, nisi ut aliquid ex ea commodi consequatur. Duis aute laborum reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.
- Point 03:** Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrum exercitationem ullam corporis suscipit laboriosam, nisi ut aliquid ex ea commodi consequatur. Duis aute laborum reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

01. Amon

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MORE INFO:
<https://www.fbk.eu/press-releases/direct-use-of-ammonia-in-fuel-cells/>

ONLINE (LOCKED):
<https://ammonia.eu/>

02. Table A

The Smart Ammonia Questionnaire used to collect data from the six resorts is divided in 7 sections. The structure is shown below:

SECTION	SUBSECTION	DESCRIPTION
01 TITLE	Sub-01a	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-01b	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-01c	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-01d	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
02 TITLE	Sub-02a	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-02b	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
03 TITLE	Sub-03a	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-03b	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-03c	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
04 TITLE	Sub-04a	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
	Sub-04b	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed eiusmod tempor incidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

03. Icons and data

	999 Kw/h Power	99 Kw * of Power Divs	1 * of SOFC
	100 km ² Area	10 * of SOFC	10 * of Burners
	10 Boats per day	999 l Ammonia	100% Renewable-energy
	20 Sites per boat	999 l Ammonia	100% Renewable-energy

05kg CO2 emissions

05. Infographic

06. Table C

05. Infographic

08. Ammon

08. Ammon

Ammon - Ammonia to power

Coordinator Contacts:
 Matteo **2024** (FBK) | matteo.2024@fbk.eu | www.fbk.eu | ammonia.eu | www.cleanhydrogen.eu

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, under Grant Agreement No. 101012161

Figure 6. AMON Template for Word documents

3.2 The website and social media

Although the **project website** is usually considered part of the visual identity package², it is one of the most used tools to communicate with the public.

With its user-friendly design, simple structure and a semi-technical language, AMON website – available at <https://www.amon-project.eu> – describes the project objectives and technology to multiple audiences: academic and professional stakeholders operating in the ammonia and hydrogen field, industries, policymakers, and citizens in Europe and worldwide.

Furthermore, on the website, in the *Result webpage*, it is currently possible to find the Dissemination and Communication materials, while presentations and posters presented during events and news about the developments of the project will be included once available. All the published news is posted on AMON social media: LinkedIn and Twitter³.

Figure 7. Screenshot of AMON Website - Results webpage

As reported in D5.2, LinkedIn is a social network that is mainly preferred by professionals and business managers, but also liked by academic and research centers. Twitter communicates with short posts known as tweets and it is a tool often used by policymakers.

² A more detailed description of the project website and social media can be found in deliverable *D5.2 Visual Identity*

³ AMON Social Media: LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/amon-project-eu/> and Twitter: <https://twitter.com/AmonProjectEU>

Since the launch of the website in June 2023, seven news have been published on the social media, and five news on the website.

Table 2. AMON Communication Activities

Date	Title	Partner	Tool	
			Website	Social media
June 2023	AMON Project kicked off	FBK	x	x
June 2023	First Conference for AMON	FBK / SE	x	x
14 June 2023	AMON presented at the NH ₃ Event Europe 2023	ALSW	x	x
22 June 2023	Launch of website	FBK		x
27 June 2023	AMON First Project meeting	FBK / DTU	x	x
4 July 2023	AMON reached 100 followers on LinkedIn	-		LinkedIn
20 July 2023	AMON has a flyer	FBK	x	x

A proper editorial plan has not yet been created as the project has not yet reached concrete results to be shown in conferences and events. With the increasing number of news, an editorial plan will be set.

3.3 Press releases and articles on magazine

As reported in the Grant Agreement, AMON will have to publish at least two press releases: one at the beginning and one at the end of the project.

The first has been published already and is available at this link: <https://amon-project.eu/2023/01/31/amon-project-kicked-off/>

D5.1 describes the objective of the press release, the partners who published it, through with tools and on which platform, and the number of visualisations received.

This first article has the purpose to inform all stakeholder groups of the launch of the project, while the last will outline the results achieved.

AMON Partners are aware that these two press releases consist in the minimum number of publication and do not exclude the possibility of publishing articles on non-scientific magazines.

Some examples can be online magazines such as FBK Magazine, HydroNews, Hydrogen Tech World⁴, or national newspapers.

⁴ HydroNews: <https://hydronews.it/> | Hydrogen Tech World: <https://hydrogentechworld.com/>

3.4 Branding Guidelines

The document contains the rules on how to appropriately use AMON visual identity and branding elements like the logo, colours, and typography. These guidelines are relevant to ensure that all partners, but also external stakeholders, are aware of and understand the AMON identity, the concept behind it and how to make use of it in the most appropriate way.

For example, brand guidelines are a useful resource during on-boarding of new members in the project's partners, to smooth processes and to have a set of rules and standards to communicate consistently the AMON identity.

The document outlines:

- The concept description with the logo and pictogram. Logo and pictogram are in colour, white and black versions.
- The how to and the restrictions in the use the logo
- The colour palette with meaning and codes, and example of colour applications
- The logo construction lines, clearance spaces and minimum sizes to guarantee its readability.
- The typography to be used in the logo and pay-off.
- Instructions on how to acknowledge the EU Funding: The Clean Hydrogen Partnership, EU flag and acknowledgement to be included in publications, presentations, poster etc.
- Instructions on how to include the branding on infrastructures and equipment funded by AMON Project. The rules were taken from the Visual Identity Manual⁵ of the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.

The document also reports:

- Sample images that can be used with the AMON logo on it. The images have been taken from free stock of photos.
- 3D images of the technology and its applications, which have been elaborated by the subcontractor and are part of AMON Visual identity.
- Example of infographics.
- Example of applications of the visual identity: on the roll-up, on caps and flyers.
- The string of partners logos with the Clean Hydrogen acknowledgement.
- Templates of the PowerPoint presentation and Word document created.

Two versions of the guidelines have been created. One version indicates the partners where to download the communication materials, as some links were included connected to the SharePoint. The second version is without links and has been published on the AMON website⁶, in the D&C Materials section of the "Result" web page. The email address to contact for any additional questions regarding the use of the AMON logo and visual identity is included in the document.

⁵ Clean Hydrogen Partnership, Visual Identity Manual https://www.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/media/visual-identity_en

⁶ The Branding guidelines on the AMON Website: <https://amon-project.eu/results/>

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01. Concept

USE AND CONVERSION OF AMMONIA INTO HIGH EFFICIENCY ELECTRICITY USING A SOLID OXIDE FUEL CELL

- #start
- #molecule
- #transformation
- #cell
- #energy
- #future
- #simplicity

01. Concept

The logo is characterized by the 'a' molecule that focuses itself on the 'a' the part of the letter including a passage from one environment to another.

Another arrangement is the symbol of the ignition 'ON' which, as a part of the circle, emphasizes the reaction.

The logo also represents an initial and endogenous hydrocarbon generation.

The project defines the concept.

02. Logo

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

03. Pictogram

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

04. Use of the Logo

The logo and pictogram shall be used in its entirety without distorting, modifying or repeating the design elements. The logo and pictogram shall be used by the team in conferences, meetings and events where AMON is present. The logo and pictogram may be used for a limited period subject to the following terms and conditions:

- permission is requested and granted before the logo is used.
- Request for permission can be submitted to the Communication Team by e-mail: inf@amonfc.com
- It is not allowed to commercialize products or activities which are incompatible with the aims and principles of the project.

Key Messages:
The brand cannot be defined. The visual and conceptual changes do not use shadow or just the outline. The single color is changed.

05. Color palette

water, freedom, atmosphere

earth, chemical reaction, green energy

Main Blue #002060

Main Green #008000

06. Construction lines

07. Clearance space

The protection area of the logo is highly recommended to guarantee the visual integrity and clear identification of the logo and project in the different applications.

08. Color applications

09. Typography of the Logo

LOGO TYPEFACE
Typo Round Bold

SECONDARY TYPEFACE
DOSIS

LOGO TYPEFACE
amoni
AMMONIA TO POWER

SECONDARY TYPEFACE
Aa Aa Aa Aa Aa
MICH DENVER BUDAPEST VIENNA SYRACUSE

ABCDEF GHIKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
€@ 1234567890 *\$%&#

SUPPORT TYPEFACE (for text paragraph)
RUBIK
ABCDEF GHIKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
€@ 1234567890 *\$%&#

10. Minimum size

The minimum size for the logo should be respected to guarantee its readability.

The minimum width for the complete logo is 3 cm.

The minimum width for the logo without the payoff is 2 cm.

The minimum width for the tagline is 1 cm.

11. Sample Images

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

11. Sample Images

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

12. Infographics

$NH_3 \rightarrow E$
AMMONIA TO POWER

AMMONIA
 $H-N-H$
|
H

AMMONIA - NH3 - Vapor Pressure

Pressure (bar)

Temperature (deg C)

AMMONIA POWER NAVAL INDUSTRY HOUSE

13. Applications

14. Acknowledgement of EU funding

As a beneficiary of the Clean Hydrogen Partnership, AMON has the right obligation to acknowledge EU funding received.

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

The branding of any communication material (including information material, brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, equipment and infrastructure) needs to apply the following rules:

- Display the Clean Hydrogen Partnership logo
- Display the EU emblem. Not funded by the European Union. It appears in the background.
- Include the disclaimer:
 - Who is displayed in a special way with other logos (e.g. other partners)
 - The Partnership logo and emblem must be displayed in each communication and visibility via the other logos. The logos shall be visible in the website without disturbing modifications regarding the common elements.

15. Logos of Partners

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

Logos of partner institutions including E.ON Energy Research Center, SolyEris, ABB Laval Technologies, SAPIO, kiwa, VTT, DTU, EPFL, and HSLU Hochschule Luzern.

15. Logos of Partners

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

Partner logos to be included in reports and website with dark backgrounds

16. Report template

17. Presentation template

The template should be used both for internal meetings and external events, where AMON is represented

[LINK DOWNLOAD](#)

18. Branding of infrastructure

Any infrastructure, equipment, vehicle, supplies or major is built funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership must acknowledge EU support and also by the European flag, Clean Hydrogen Partnership and AMON emblem (included in the local languages, where appropriate). Production of any branding material (typically included in the user responsibility of the beneficiary and is not supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership).

Typically, all funding partners are acknowledged on each equipment. The Clean Hydrogen Partnership logo and the EU emblem used by other same sites as other funding partners, under no circumstances should they be smaller than the logo of other funding partners.

Next to the above, the logo of AMON should be located.

The logos should be clearly visible and be easy to be the size of the equipment.

Minimum size for small applications: 50 x 30 cm
Minimum size for large applications: 50 x 50 cm

Figure 8. Screenshot of AMON Branding Guidelines

3.5 Poster

A poster presentation is one of the most used tools by researchers.

A poster is a single document, usually in the size of a A0 – 841 x 1189 mm – with graphics and images and condensed information.

Usually, during congress or conferences with an academic or professional focus, there are poster sessions that encourage the discussion among researchers, professionals, and experts of a certain field.

The below poster is just an example. The logo of the presenting partner can be added next to the acknowledgement. The 3D images can be substituted with other images of the project (chapter 3.7), such as icons, infographics, and sample images.

The logo and acknowledgement are elements that cannot be removed.

Figure 9. AMON Poster Template

3.6 Roll-up

Roll ups are appreciated tools in fairs and events with numerous people.

The success is due to the practical use of these banners that can be easily transported and assembled and give a clear and immediate visual impact.

The roll-up does not usually include much information. The banner of AMON includes the main 3D image of the technology in a possible environment, the logo of the project and the string with the logos of the partners and of the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.

The roll up of AMON will be used in project meetings and events organized by the project.

Figure 10. AMON Roll-up

3.7 Media Library: Infographics and 3D images

During the process of conceptualization and creation of the main illustrations of the website and flyer, several ideas were transformed into (i) icons that express a single specific concept, and (ii) 3D images of the technology and its components, as well as the technology and its possible applications.

The external provider also found sample images from free-credit stocks to be used in leaflets or presentations.

Figure 11. Icons and infographics

Figure 12. Sample images

Figure 13. 3D Images

All these materials that constitutes a media library, can be used by partners in presentations and posters.

All materials are available on the shared virtual space created on SharePoint by FBK.

Figure 14. Screenshot of the AMON repository

3.8 GIFs

GIF is the acronym of Graphics Interchange Format, which is widely used by social media and in social media marketing as it is an animated graphic photo that wishes to send a clear and concise message and/or graphically represent more complex concepts. The GIF is immediately eye-catching and easily shareable across multiple social networks. These animated images build awareness of brands and make it more vital and appealing to multiple stakeholder groups.

After the work done to transform the future technology into a 3D image, this was animated by the external provider.

Fundamental is how the GIF shows how the technology should work and therefore (1) the flow of ammonia, which first enters the cracker and then proceed in the SOFC before becoming energy, and (2) the heat and hydrogen flows, 3) the interactions of the whole system (Figure 15).

The animated GIF appears on the *Prototype* webpage of the website and can be watched [at this link](https://amon-project.eu/prototype/), where there is also the possibility to look at it from the above.

Figure 15. Screenshot of the video of AMON Technology - <https://amon-project.eu/prototype/>

Another GIF was then created and shows the technology in the possible environments (Figure 16): the harbour and the boat - focus of the AMON project, but also the stationary use in industries and telecommunication/data centres. The GIF is on the homepage of the website and can be watched [at this link](#).

Figure 16. Screenshot of the video of AMON Technology and applications - <https://amon-project.eu/>

3.9 The flyer: digital and printed versions

The flyer is an 8-page leaflet, whose main purpose is to present the project, its objectives and main result to a wide audience. The flyer does not describe in detail the concept but gives an overview which is easily accessible also to the less scientific public. The document can be attached to emails to introduce the project and can also be printed and easily transported to conferences, fairs, and events.

In the outer part, the flyer outlines the objectives of the project, the main actor of the technology - e.g. ammonia, and the members of the Consortium with the acknowledgement to the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.

In the inner part, the image of the technology with all components is reported, with the three possible applications of the technology, but with a strong focus on the harbors and naval industry where the technology will be tested.

Ammonia

Ammonia production accounts for around 45% of current global hydrogen consumption. Replacing conventional ammonia with renewable ammonia produced from renewable hydrogen presents an early opportunity for action in decarbonising the chemical sector. As a transportable and storable energy carrier with high hydrogen energy content, it assists the H₂ economy and promotes a new flexible stationary power generation.

amoni
AMMONIA TO POWER
Development of a next generation AMONiA Fuel Cell system

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PARTNER

EPIC - European Power Infrastructure Centre	Solvay	SAPIO - Sustainable Ammonia Production	kiwa
VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland	DTU - Technical University of Denmark	EPFL - École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	HSLU - Hochschule für Technik und Naturwissenschaften

The project is supported by the **Clean Hydrogen Partnership** and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Council Research under Grant Agreement No 101101821

AMON Objectives

AMON will develop a novel system for the utilization and conversion of ammonia into electric power at high efficiency using a Solid Oxide Fuel Cell system. The project will:

- Design and develop a fuel cell stack module at a scale of 8 kWel, tested and qualified to convert ammonia into power, possibly using the internal reforming capacity of a solid oxide cell operating at high temperature and managing the power output through the control of the cell fuel utilization.
- Qualify a system 100% tolerant to ammonia in all the components and related materials.
- Target 70% system electric efficiency.
- Qualify the system for at least 3000 hrs operation with demonstrated 90% availability in the operating hours and less than 3% degradation rate at nominal power condition measured over 1000 hours of continuous operation.

Redistribution of energy

AMON can be a major change in sectors requiring an energy carrier provider of high energy density, long term storage capacity and easy transportability. AMON can provide a fuel for stationary power, with capacity to displace coal and natural gas in both base loads and peaks at large and small scales. Diesel in back-up and off-grid applications can be replaced by Ammonia with Solid-Oxide Fuel Cells; several options are among the most promising and efficient solutions for defossilisation of different energy sectors. AMON can contribute to the decarbonisation of autonomous power systems operated on a liquid carbon-free fuel in the digital data transmission sector and telecommunications within a reasonable timeframe.

AMON system

The technology concept of AMON is a system able to convert ammonia into power very efficiently. The integrated zero-carbon power generation system will consist of a SOFC stack, a cracker and other balance of plant components.

Harbours and naval industry

AMON can be a profitable solution in the maritime sector to be utilized in port areas and onboard ships, using direct electrification of several services. Once validated in the lab, the AMON final system will become a demonstrator, hosted by SAPIO to perform tests on its premises in Porto Marghera, Venice (Italy). The tests will be performed to target the total testing time foreseen for AMON - at least 3.000 hours, including one single long-term test of 1000 hours, reaching out 90% of system availability and checking that the final performances are aligned with the project objectives.

Figure 17. AMON Flyer: printing version

Ammonia

Ammonia production accounts for around 45% of current global hydrogen consumption. Replacing conventional ammonia with renewable ammonia produced from renewable hydrogen presents an early opportunity for action in decarbonising the chemical sector. As a transportable and storable energy carrier with high hydrogen energy content, it adds the H₂ economy and promotes a new flexible stationary power generation.

N

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{NH}_3 \\ | \\ \text{H}-\text{N}-\text{H} \\ | \\ \text{H} \end{array}$$

AMON Objectives

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amoni
AMMONIA TO POWER

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Figure 18. AMON Flyer: digital version

04. Planned activities

Consequently, from the list outlined in the GA, the missing tools at the current project stage (August 2023) are:

- Factsheets
- Final Brochure
- Video
- Newsletter

Considering that the project is in its first year, Partners have agreed during the first project meeting – which took place in DTU, at the end of June – that the materials currently available are enough for this initial stage. The missing tools will be created when results will start to be concrete, and the materials will have to be updated.

4.1 Video

Considering that the project already has 2 videos of how the technology should look like in 3D version, it has been decided that the short video of 2-4 minutes would be more attractive if it shows the pilot installation or the prototype and with interviews of members. The conceptualisation of the video can start in the summer 2024 and will continue depending on the advancements of the project.

The video will be disseminated via website, YouTube, partners communication channels, and used as a supporting communication tool in all events.

4.2 Factsheets

A fact sheet is a one-page document that provides information on a specific topic in an easy and quick-to-read format, with images, graphs, and data. It can be specific on a topic or just have the goal to promote the subject to which it is related. AMON factsheets can be designed either focusing on the components or illustrating a procedure and process addressing a specific target user or stakeholders.

4.3 Final Brochure

The brochure will consist of a 16-page document and will be the final material of the AMON Project, gathering and describing all the activities done and results achieved. The document will contain key information on the technology, which can amplify its exploitation potential as it will be mainly addressed to the scientific community and industrial stakeholders, but it might also be intended to raise the interests of policy makers or investors.

4.4 Newsletter

Partners will discuss about the possibility of having a yearly newsletter, starting from the end of the first year, e.g. 2023.

Conclusions

This document describes the communication materials that will be used for the dissemination and communication activities of the project.

This report is based on D5.2 of AMON as visual identity is the *fil rouge* of the materials created. Part of this report will also be included in the definition of the D&C Plan which will report the set of activities for targeting multiple stakeholders and achieving the D&C targets set in the Grant Agreement.

Communication materials will greatly contribute to the dissemination of the project and support the exploitation of the AMON Key Exploitable Results, in line with the objectives set by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, under Grant Agreement No 101101521

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Amon – Ammonia to power

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